
ULTRASONIC BATHS EQUIPMENT FOR VARIOUS LABORATORIES.

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Annotatsiya: Ushbu matnda tozalash va sterilizatsiya qilish uchun ultratovushli vannalardan foydalanish muhokama qilinadi. U ultratovushli vannalardan foydalanishning samaradorligi va iqtisodiy afzalliklarini ta'kidlab, ularning tozalash vaqtini qisqartirish va samaradorlikni oshirish qobiliyatini ta'kidlaydi. Matnda, shuningdek, maxsus o'rnatish talablari va sotib olishdan oldin biriktirilgan bo'limni o'qish muhimligi qayd etilgan. U ultratovushli vannalarning turli xil narsalarni tozalash va yog 'parchalari va kimyoviy qoldiqlar kabi ifloslantiruvchi moddalarni olib tashlash uchun yaroqliligini tekshiradi.

Kalit so'zlar: Ultrasonik vannalar, Samaradorlik, Iqtisodiy nuqtai nazar, Tozalash vaqti, Tozalash samaradorligi, O'qitish maqsadlari, Amaliy qiymat, O'rnatish talablari, Inventarlarni tozalash, Laboratoriya tajribalari.

Annotation: This text discusses the use of ultrasonic baths for cleaning and sterilization. He highlights the efficiency and economic benefits of using ultrasonic baths, emphasizing their ability to reduce cleaning time and increase efficiency. The text also mentions special installation requirements and the importance of reading the attached chapter before purchasing. It investigates the suitability of ultrasonic baths for cleaning various objects and removing contaminants such as fat fragments and chemical residues.

Key words: Ultrasonic baths, Efficiency, Economic point of view, Cleaning time, Cleaning efficiency, Teaching goals, Practical value, Installation requirements, Inventory cleaning, Laboratory experiments.

Аннотация: В этом тексте обсуждается использование ультразвуковых ванн для очистки и стерилизации. Он подчеркивает эффективность и экономические преимущества использования ультразвуковых ванн, подчеркивая их способность сокращать время очистки и повышать эффективность. В тексте также упоминаются особые требования к установке и важность ознакомления с прилагаемой главой перед покупкой. В нем исследуется пригодность ультразвуковых ванн для очистки различных предметов и удаления загрязнений, таких как фрагменты жира и химические остатки.

Ключевые слова: Ультразвуковые ванны, Эффективность, Экономическая точка зрения, Время очистки, Эффективность очистки,

Учебные цели, Практическая ценность, Требования к установке, Уборка инвентаря, Лабораторные эксперименты.

The use of ultrasonic baths is excused after all aspects of efficiency. Their use is appropriate from the economic point of view. Due to its peculiarity, the transmitted purification order helps to shorten the purification time and increase its efficiency. Ultra sonic baths adapt in training targets and in production. They are as practical as practical value. Ultrasonic baths have specific requirements for their installation, as shown below. On the eve of their purchase, the provided chapter is inevitable for review.

The ultrasonic bath, that is, washing, freely adapts for the sake of cleaning inventory, as well as conducting experiments. Spread in more detail we will examine the issues of using ultrasonic baths in the laboratory [1].

The ultrasonic bath is suitable for cleaning:

- test tubes and tubes;
- bowl and chemical containers, as well as other equipment.
- Removed contaminants include:
- fat fragments;
- fragments of other chemical reactions.

Or, in a laboratory ultrasonic cleaner, it is possible to sift a variety of contaminants. The property and degree of purification awakens to be conditioned exclusively through the selection of a washing agent. To the great superiority of the order of cleansing provided is solicitude. Using ultrasound, you will not spoil your instruments as if during mechanical processing. The frugality of the finish is achieved after the L/C result of cavitation through ultrasound. With all this, the result is "microexplosions" of areas with tiny and huge pressure, which do not harm the surface to be cleaned [2].

By using the passed method, you are more likely to inherit an immaculately sparkling orb compared to other methods. Slush particles leave no traces, they come off and get into the sediment. The skill doesn't end with cleaning. Ultrasonic baths are widely used for sterilization of instruments. The reality of sterilization, for all this, is extended many times after comparison with ordinary methods [3].

Figure 1. Ultrasonic bath.

It is worth addressing your passion for cleaning performance issues. In the end of the experiments it was fixed that there is a conditioned lack of independence between the frequency of cleansing and the effect, some is observed. But this dependence is not a bisector and not linear! So it turned out that the radio frequency of 40 kHz seems to be optimal. Actually, it is suitable for the sake of a deterrent amount of pollution. However, in cases where sometimes the particles of slush are tiny, it is appropriate to multiply the frequency of emission in order to increase the corporate efficiency of the process. The graph below shows the effect of emission frequency and performance dependence on particle size [4].

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The overall validity of cleaning depends on a variety of conditions, starting with the geometry of the object and the detergent.

In addition to the service of ultrasonic equipment as a kind of "cleaner" in laboratories, it also found experimental use.

When working on projects, it is used for:

- emulsification, creation of stable emulsions;

- performing chemical reactions, where sound looks like a stimulus for the process;
- sleep chemistry with the intensification of biotechnological processes, chemical and physical;
- diffusion acceleration;
- sonic sono-chemical water treatment;
- emulsification for the sake of categorical bodies;

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